

In-Silico Studies of KRAS, CALML3, ERBB3, CRABP1, RRP7A Proteins Involved in Gastric Cancer

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Abstract:

Gastric cancer is the third leading cause of global cancer-related mortality and is challenging to manage due to genetic risk factors, tumour heterogeneity, and metastatic progression. In this study, five proteins- RRP7A, ERBB3, CALML3, CRABP1, and KRAS were selected as they play a crucial role in tumour growth and survival through cell cycle regulation, signal transduction, and retinoic acid metabolism. The proteins were retrieved from NCBI and UniProtKb. Sequence similarity was analysed using BLAST, and multiple sequence alignment was performed using Clustal Omega. Three-dimensional structures were generated using SWISS-MODEL and validated using SAVES v6.0. The Active site prediction was carried out using CASTp and molecular docking was performed using PyRx (AutoDock Vina). Protein- ligand interactions were analysed using BIOVIA Discovery Studio. The generated models of gastric cancer-associated proteins demonstrated structural stability with acceptable validation parameters. Molecular docking studies with Irinotecan, 5-fluorouracil, Apatinib, and trifluridine predicted favourable binding positions, interaction patterns, and binding affinities. The results indicating that these targets are suitable for further therapeutic investigation. However, further experimental validation is required to confirm and validate the computational studies.

Keywords: Gastric Cancer, Protein Modelling, Molecular Docking, Protein-Ligand Interaction.

INTRODUCTION:

Gastric cancer is one of the major causes of cancer-related deaths worldwide and ranks as the third leading cause of global cancer mortality. In many patients, clinical symptoms appear only in later stages, which makes early detection difficult (Chia NY, 2016). The occurrence of gastric cancer increases with age, and nearly 10% of cases are diagnosed before the age of 45 years. The prognosis for advanced gastric cancer remains poor, with survival often reported to be less than 12 months (Machlowska, 2020)

The five target proteins selected for the Gastric cancer are KRAS (GTPase protein) CALML3 (Calmodulin like protein 3), ERBB3 (Erb-B2 Receptor Tyrosine Kinase 3), CRABP1 (Cellular retinoic acid binding protein 1), RRP7A (Ribosomal RNA processing 7 homolog A

)and its crucial role in gastric cancer are: KRAS- Mutation of KRAS at codons 12 and 13 leads to constitutive activation of the RAS/RAF/MEK/ERK signalling pathway in gastric cancer. This promotes uncontrolled cell proliferation and tumour progression. although KRAS mutation are present in a small subset of gastric cancer (5-7%). They are associated with poor prognosis. KRAS activation has also been associated with epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) and increased metastatic potential(Hewitt LC, 2019).CALML3- Calmodulin like protein 3 is a calcium binding protein, downregulation of CALML3 expression is observed in gastric cancer and is associated with increased tumour cells proliferation and malignant progression. Loss or reduced CALML3 expression may facilitate uncontrolled cell growth(Guangxia Chen, 2019). ERBB3- ERBB3 (HER3) is a member of the EGFR/ERBB receptor family that contributes to gastric cancer progression by activating downstream pathways, especially PI3K/AKT. Over-expression of ERBB3 is frequently observed in advanced gastric cancer and is associated with aggressive tumor behaviour and poorer prognosis(Byeon SJ, 2017). CRABP1- Cellular retinoic acid binding protein 1 promotes proliferation, migration, and invasion of gastric cancer cells. High CRABP1 expression in tumors correlates with increased epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) and a higher incidence of peritoneal recurrence after surgery. Elevated CRABP1 is also associated with poorer disease-free survival in gastric cancer patients(Sakata K, 2022). RRP7A- Ribosomal RNA processing 7 homolog A is involved in rRNA processing and ribosome biogenesis. Dysregulated ribosome biogenesis supports tumor cell growth and survival in aggressive cancers. RRP7A was originally identified as a gastric cancer- associated antigen (CTA-126B4.3). Its expression may contribute to gastric tumor progression(A. Lin?, 2002) Diagnosis is performed primarily by upper Gastrointestinal Endoscopy with histological biopsy and staging using contrast-enhanced CT and endoscopic ultrasound to know about tumor depth(Smyth, 2020). Treatment involves Radical Gastrectomy with perioperative for advanced stages Systemic Chemotherapy, Her2-targeted therapy and immune checkpoint inhibitors have improved overall survival outcomes(D' Amico TA, 2022)

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The Five target and template protein sequences were retrieved from the NCBI database based on the sequence length of less than 250 amino acids. Sequence similarity analysis was performed using BLAST to identify suitable template proteins. Multiple sequence alignment between the target and template sequences was carried out using Clustal Omega to identify conserved regions and mismatches. The Three-dimensional structures of the selected proteins were generated using the SWISS-MODEL server. The generated models were validated using the SAVES v6.0 server to assess structural reliability. Active site and pocket prediction was performed using CASTp. Ligand molecules (IRINOTECAN, 5- FLUOROURACIL, APATINIB, TRIFLURIDINE) were selected from the PubChem database. Molecular docking using PyRx integrated with AutoDock Vina to evaluate binding affinities. Protein– ligand interactions were visualized using BIOVIA Discovery Studio.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

HOMOLOGY MODELLING:

The accession codes (NP_005176.1, NP_004369.1, P01116.1, AAB26935.1, AAK68659.1) corresponding to calmodulin-like protein 3, cellular retinoic acid-binding protein1, GTPase KRAS, receptor tyrosine kinase, gastric cancer antigen Zg14, partial (2) were retrieved from the NCBI database. The respective FASTA sequences were then obtained from UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot for further analysis. To identify suitable template protein BLAST search was performed. Template proteins showing more than 27% sequence identity and > 70% query coverage were considered for model construction. The relevance of sequence similarity in template selection has been discussed previously (Webb B, 2016)

The templates selected showed less than 10% unmodeled regions. Multiple sequence alignment was carried out using Clustal Omega tool to examine conserved and variable regions between the target and template protein(Sievers F, 2011).

PROTEIN MODELLING:

The target protein models were generated using the SWISS MODEL SERVER for the prediction of 3D protein structures. The 3d structures of the protein models are selected based on the GMQE AND QMEAN QUALITY SCORES(Benkert, 2009) and the GMQE value should be >0.8 and sequence identity >80%. Therefore, the finalized models are downloaded in PDB format for further model validation.

MODEL VALIDATION:

The generated protein models were validated using the SAVES v6.1 validation program. After running the program, the results correspond to validation tools such as Verify3D and ProCheck. Verify3D checks whether the 3D structure is compatible with its amino acid sequence (1D)(Eisenberg, 1997) The Ramachandran plot checks whether the backbone dihedral angles (psi) & (phi) are energetically present in the allowed regions(Laskowski, n.d.) If more than 80% of the amino acid residues are present in the favourable allowed region, it indicates a good homology model. The 5 proteins having 91.5%, 96.1%, 91.8%, 88.3%, 91.3% amino acid residues are present in the favourable regions. Therefore, it is considered a good homology model.

ACTIVE SITE PREDICTION:

The Prediction of Active Sites and pockets in a protein was performed using Castp (Computed Atlas Surface Topography of Proteins) helps us to understand how potential ligands interact or bind with the target protein effectively(Naghibzadeh, 2003)

SELECTION OF LIGANDS:

The four anti-gastric cancer drugs (IRINOTECAN, 5-FLUOROURACIL, APATINIB and TRIFLURIDINE) were selected for the treatment of the gastric cancer. The 3D and 2D structures were acquired from PubChem database and downloaded in SDF Format, which is saved in PDB Format using Discovery Studio.

MOLECULAR DOCKING:

Docking was performed between the target protein and the selected ligands using PyRx software (Autodock Vina). The docking process generates 9 poses or orientations based on the protein-ligand complex. The docking results provide Binding affinity values(kcal/mol) and RMSD values and binding affinity values represent the strength of interaction between the protein and the ligand, where more negative values indicate stronger and more stable binding(Eberhardt, 2021)

SPLITTING OF LIGANDS: The splitting of ligands was performed using Autodock vina_split. The command line tool separated the multi-model PDBQT files into 9 individual conformations or pose. The best pose or orientation was selected based on lowest binding affinity and acceptable RMSD value.

VISUALIZATION OF PROTEIN-LIGAND INTERACTIONS:

The 3D and 2D structures and interactions between the protein-ligands are visualized using BIOVIA Discovery Studio. It provides the category or type of interaction and the distance of the amino acids in non-bond interactions. All five proteins interacted with their respective ligands and exhibited multiple conventional hydrogen bonds along with π -alkyl and carbon-hydrogen interactions. For comparative analysis and due to space limitations, three representative conventional hydrogen bonds per protein, along with one π -alkyl and one carbon-hydrogen interaction, were selected for discussion. The observed hydrogen bond distances ranged between 1.5–3.0 Å, indicating strong and favourable binding interactions. The detailed 2D and 3D interaction analyses and the summarized interaction data are provided in the following tables and figures.

3D AND 2D INTERACTIONS BETWEEN PROTEINS-LIGANDS

SUMMARY TABLE OF INTERACTION:

RRP7A WITH 4 LIGANDS:

NAME	DISTANCE	INTERACTIONS
A: SER67 -: UNK0: O5	2.73181	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
A: ARG72 -: UNK0: O3	3.12018	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
A: HIS77: A: SER73: O	2.93715	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
A: ARG72: UNK0: O7	2.83873	Conventional Hydrogen Bond

KRAS WITH 4 LIGANDS:

NAME	DISTANCE	INTERACTIONS
A: LYS 169 -: UNK0: O5	2.94842	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
A: SER39- A: ASP54	3.32129	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
A: ARG135: A: GLN13	2.89075	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
A: ARG97: UNK0: F2	3.47365	Conventional Hydrogen Bond

CALML3 WITH 4 LIGANDS:

NAME	DISTANCE	INTERACTIONS
A: ILE86: N-A: ASN82:O	3.10026	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
A: ARG75: UNK0: O2	3.15416	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
A: ASN82- A: ASP79	3.23495	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
A: GLU83-A: ASP79	3.00678	Conventional Hydrogen Bond

ERBB3 WITH 4 LIGANDS:

NAME	DISTANCE	INTERACTIONS
A: GLU57 -A: ALA27	2.79283	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
A: THR32: -: UNK0	3.14458	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
A: UNK0: H46 -: UNK0	2.09716	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
A: SER75: - A: ASP73	3.03889	Conventional Hydrogen Bond

CRABP1 WITH 4 LIGANDS:

NAME	DISTANCE	INTERACTIONS
A: ARG132 -: UNK0:O6	2.93761	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
B: ARG60 -: UNK0:O2	2.99995	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
A: ALA37: A: ALA33:O	3.25881	Conventional Hydrogen Bond
A: LYS31 -: UNK0:F2	3.11848	Conventional Hydrogen Bond

CONCLUSION:

Gastric cancer is often diagnosed at advanced stages, due to which the treatment options are limited and less survival. In this in silico study we observed strong interactions between key gastric cancer protein- KRAS, CALML3, CRABP1, ERBB3, RRP7A and the therapeutic ligands such as Irinotecan, 5- fluorouracil, Apatinib, Trifluridine. Molecular docking results reveal that Apatinib drug molecule has stronger binding affinity with CRABP1, CALML3, ERBB3, RRP7A and 5-flourouracil molecule has stronger binding affinity with KRAS. The interactions observed at specific amino acid residues: LYS169 & ARG135 in KRAS, GLU37 & THR32 in ERBB3, ARG60 & ALA37 in CRABP1, ILE86 & GLU83 in CALML3, SER67 & ARG72 IN RRP7A, by targeting these residues could disrupt the functional role of proteins which interfere the signalling pathways that trigger tumor growth and progression. Over all these findings highlight proteins are promising therapeutic targets in gastric cancer. As these are computational simulations, further in-vitro and in-vivo studies are required to validate their clinical effectiveness.

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